

METHODOLOGICAL IMPROVEMENT OF ENGLISH LESSONS IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the formation of pedagogical-methodical competence of the future elementary English teacher with the help of modern technologies and In English is taught to the younger generation from preschool and elementary grades different ways and ways of going are considered and studied. Theirs to the younger generation there are many advantages of teaching foreign languages from childhood.*

Keywords: *young generation, preschool education, primary education, interest, form, methods.*

Today, the ability to know foreign languages is one of the integral parts of our life. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, their demand for language learning is high. People learn such knowledge first in pre-school educational institutions, and then at school, in institutes, training courses or independently. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and skills of teachers.

The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. A step-by-step approach to teaching English based on the learner's potential, level, and age gives good results. According to psychologists, children learn languages faster and easier than adults.

One of the most fundamental and positive changes in modern primary education is the decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" is Resolution No. PQ-1875. Based on this decision, learning of foreign languages, mainly English, in the form of game-style lessons and oral speech lessons from the 1st grade of general secondary schools, and alphabet, reading and grammar from the 2nd grade. teaching begins step by step. According to the decision, under the leadership of the Coordinating Council, which is constantly working on the further development of foreign language learning, in all directions of the educational field, an incomparable scale of work has been started.

For example, since the 2013-2014 academic year, continuous teaching of foreign languages in the form of game-style exercises and oral speech lessons has been started in the first grades of secondary schools. Also, textbooks and teaching-methodical sets for these classes were created. It is worth noting that the games in the complexes created for the first grades are proportional to the age of the children. Children begin their first acquaintance with a foreign language by learning the culture of greetings, colors and everyday words in the form of a dialogue. The acceleration of globalization processes in the world, the transition to free market relations and the promotion of the introduction of high technologies in production increase the need for "linguistic capital", i.e. specialists who have a perfect command of foreign languages (especially English).

In order to ensure quality and efficiency in foreign language education, the experience of reducing the age of learning/teaching foreign languages is becoming popular. This was caused by the widespread concept of "the younger the better / early is better". The decision to include English in the primary education curriculum was approved based on the following conclusions: Critical Period Hypothesis states that there is a limited developmental period during which it is possible to acquire a language, be it L1 or L2, to normal, nativelike levels. - The Critical Period Hypothesis asserts that there is a limited period of development in a foreign language, whether it is a native or a foreign language, when it can be acquired at a level close to natural speech. Learning and teaching a foreign language, especially English, from a young age has its own history. While learning and teaching English from a young age was first experienced in upper-class families (Anna-and-the-King-of-Siam), in the 1950s it became popular in the USA and European countries, and within ten years The number of students studying on the basis of the "Foreign Language in Elementary School" program has reached one million. In France, Sweden and the Netherlands, in the mid-1950s, the English language was taught from the 3rd grade based on the "English without a book" program. In February 1997, the European Center for Modern Languages (ECML) in Graz (Austria) held an international seminar on "Foreign Language Education in Primary Schools" devoted to the problems of teaching foreign languages in primary education, in April 1997 in Warwick (England) on the topic "Warwick Euro conference on Teaching of Foreign Languages in European Primary Schools", in January 1998 in Graz on the topic "Foreign language education in primary schools - an international concern to be implemented in national contexts", 1999 in Brussels (Belgium) conference dedicated to the discussion of projects implemented to ensure quality and efficiency in English language education (Stimulating language learning: The European Label), 2007 at the State Pedagogical University named after Gersen (St. Petersburg) International seminar on methods of teaching/learning foreign languages in classrooms and problems of teacher training (Early Foreign Language Education), 2008 in Bangalore (India) aimed at popularizing international experiences of teaching foreign languages in primary education "The Way Forward: Learning from International Experience of TEYL" international conference was held. In 2013, the international scientific-practical conference held in Moscow (Russia) on the topic "Theory and practice of teaching foreign languages: traditions and innovations" also discussed the current problems of the methodology of teaching English to primary school students. At the above-mentioned seminars and conferences, recommendations were developed to ensure quality and efficiency in primary English education.

English language teaching in elementary grades: a) psychological foundations I.A.Zimnyaya (1991), D.M.Singleton (1995), D.Singleton and L.Ryan (2004), Z.Dorney (2005), P.M.Lightbone, N.Spada (2006), A.P. Sinelnikov (2009), M. Williams, R.L. Bedn (2010); b) pedagogical foundations V.A. Scott, L.H. Yetrberg (1992), S. Halliwell (1993), K. Grant (2002), J. Moon (2005), S. Horner, V. Rief (2007), A. Pinter (2011)), D. Weil, A. Fountain (2011); d) methodological foundations are detailed in the literature published by scientists such as N.D. Galskova, Z.N. Nikitenko (2004), L. Kamerun (2005), K. T. Linz, D. Newen (2005), N. A. Gorlova (2010).

A brief review of the literature on the field reveals that research has been conducted in various educational settings. Also, in some studies, children of preschool educational institutions are considered as young English language learners, while in some studies, the process of teaching English to students from 5 to 12 years of age was chosen as the object of research. In the above

literature, the term "concept" represents different concepts. The concept is used in the sense of a scientific idea(s) and defines foreign language teaching strategies and tactics at each point of the educational process. Today, the methodology of teaching English in primary education is being developed based on the educational concepts of "(Inter)Cultural Awareness", "Language Awareness" and "Humanity". (Inter)Cultural Awareness - The concept of intercultural communication was first formed in Germany and became popular in Western countries in a short time. Based on this concept, it is not necessary to teach English as a means of communication, but to develop the student in general and speech, that is, to make him interested in the English language and foreign culture, and pay attention to the language that can be encountered in everyday life. The goal is to form and develop the skills to adapt to living conditions in the integrating Europe. For this reason, in this concept, priority is given to the country studies aspect of English language education.

The educational process and content organized in the style of a game is the language of children to learn a poem introducing the customs and traditions of the country under study and will consist of songs. This concept is called "Neighbor (sister) language learning" in Europe, and the classes are mainly conducted by English speakers. In addition, in European countries, the migration of students often occurs, and they have the opportunity to live in an English-speaking environment for some time. Considering this, it is not appropriate to promote this concept in countries far from Europe and culturally different. It has been proven that learning English as a means of communication does not have the same meaning for all people everywhere in the world, and at the same time, it is difficult to simply "export" educational methods. Because, first of all, even if there is no need and opportunity to engage in communication and interaction with English speakers, it is not appropriate to teach the practical use of the language, that is, to work only on "daily speech situations" and "daily life topics". Secondly, English is the official language not only of one country, that is, Great Britain, but also of the United States of America, Australia, Canada and a number of other countries. In these countries, where the official language is English, the cultures are different. The concept of "Language Awareness" is also called "Holistic approach" and it advocates the need to master the English language as a means of acquiring new knowledge. That is, the purpose of primary English education is to acquire new knowledge about life through the medium of English. However, M. Williams and R. Bedn preferred to call Vygotsky's theory of the ontogenesis of speech development as "Holistic approach". According to them, Vygotsky would not have approved the idea of dividing the knowledge to be learned into small parts and presenting it as skills and abilities. The reason is that Vygotsky emphasizes that content should form the basis of any studied part. Under the influence of this conclusion, the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) approach is becoming popular in European countries, the United States, and countries where English is a second language.

In Uzbekistan, the concept of "Humanity" (person-oriented) has been adopted, and according to it, in primary English education, the student is given the status of the central subject of the educational process and intercultural communication (dialogue), his interest and needs are prioritized. Speech activity in English is directed to the formation of the student's personality, that is, mastering the cultural heritage created by the owner of the studied language is achieved. In the process of listening, speaking, reading, and writing, the student enriches the social, cultural, linguistic, and emotional experience previously acquired. The educational process follows didactic, psychological, linguistic, methodical and other laws. Some of them may be common to

all subjects. These laws are called the general didactic principle of education. Other laws may be specific to the teaching of certain subjects, for example; English language teaching principles.

The concept of principle has not yet been fully resolved in didactics. If one group of principles represents the regularities of the educational process, the second group of principles represents the regularities specific to a certain type of speech activity, and the third is the principles specific to a certain section of the language material. The last one is called special principles.

The term "principle" means "a basic guideline, rule". According to Ye.I. Passov, "the principle is the foundation of the so-called building of the teaching process."

The correct selection of concepts and principles ensures the effectiveness of the activities organized in the lesson, the students of junior school age increase their interest in this activity. Concepts and several dozen principles of teaching foreign languages in primary education are advanced in scientific sources. For example, the main principles of teaching foreign languages in primary education in the scientific research carried out within the framework of the project EAS 89/04, Lot 1 "Good Practice and Main Principles" carried out in 2005-2006 within the framework of the Educational and Cultural Research Program of the European Union summarized in the following order based on the criterion of importance:

- 1) choosing a meaningful context and subject suitable for the student's age (didactic);
- 2) positive approach to learning English (pedagogical);
- 3) holistic learning (methodological);
- 4) full consideration of age-related psychological and physical maturity levels of students in practical English lessons (psycholinguistic);
- 5) educating students in the spirit of tolerance towards others and respect for different values (pedagogical);
- 6) learning with the full participation of other speech analyzers, giving priority to the visual approach (applying psychological issues to the methodology);
- 7) motivation to learn English (intrinsic motivation) (psycholinguistic);
- 8) individual-oriented education, taking into account the unique characteristics of the student (pedagogical)
- 9) prioritizing listening comprehension exercises for the formation of speech (didactic);
- 10) organization of classes in the studied foreign language as much as possible (pedagogical);
- 11) consideration of students' English language learning strategies and methods (didactic).

The proposed rules and views in the practice of English language teaching are summarized and scientifically based on the status of linguodidactic (language education) principles. For example, J. Jalolov summarized the following didactic principles, despite differences in naming and essence: educational education, awareness, activity, demonstrability, systematicity (consistency), individual approach, thorough assimilation (of knowledge), such as matching student strengths. N.A. Gorlova summarized the didactic principles of teaching foreign languages in primary education as follows: activity, demonstrability, adaptation to the student's potential, individual approach, systematicity. After studying scientific sources, the didactic principles of teaching foreign languages in primary education can be summarized as follows:

1. Considering students' English language learning methods, strategies and abilities.
2. Prioritize listening comprehension exercises.
3. Creating meaningful contexts and speech situations related to the topic in lessons.

4. Extensive use of technical tools in training.
5. Use of age-appropriate authentic materials.
6. Teaching English based on speech samples.
7. Visualization of topics (using talking dolls).

Psycholinguistic principles of English language teaching in elementary grades:

Since language learning is a mental activity, it has psychological foundations. Mental activity is scientifically investigated in psychology. In this regard, there is a need to research the psychological principles of English language teaching. Two psychological principles of English language teaching have been developed in scientific sources. The psychological principles are called "verbalization" (a foreign language is learned practically only through oral speech) and "correlation" (a certain limit of the material of the English language is determined, a set of language units intended for the formation of speech skills is first formed). Despite the fact that the linguistic foundations of English language teaching have been studied to some extent, little attention has been paid to the issue of linguistic principles of English language teaching in methodological science.

In elucidating the essence of the principles of methodology, work was done based on psychological and linguistic laws, and the following psycholinguistic principles were summarized:

1. Increase students' motivation (internal drive) to learn and master English.
2. Encouraging age-appropriate physical activity of students during classes.
3. To inform students about the similarities between the mother tongue and the foreign language being studied.
4. Development of intermediate language (metalanguage) experiences of students.
5. To teach students to use the relationship between the native language and the studied foreign language.
6. General introduction of students to the structure of the English language being studied.
7. Individual approach, that is, conducting psycho-pedagogical activities taking into account the characteristics of students (the nature of each student, what he is capable of, what he is interested in, who he makes friends with, what he has a negative attitude towards).

English language teaching methodology, (a) general (speech orientation, limited and integral teaching, exercises, taking language experience into account), (b) special (teaching English based on speech samples, language practice and connection of speech practice, interdependence of types of speech activity, development of oral speech, approach to natural speech in a foreign language, acceleration of the elementary stage), (d) special (teaching grammar, teaching vocabulary, teaching the principles of winter teaching and the use of speech writing in English language teaching) have been developed. In summarizing the pedagogical principles, we considered the communicative approach to teaching foreign languages in primary education.

1. Implementation of visual approach and multisensory (fully stimulating all speech analyzers) learning. That is, a lot of exercises with the participation of analyzers of seeing, hearing, movement (speech movement and hand movement) in order to ensure thorough mastering of the educational material.

2. Teaching holistically (lexical, grammar and pronunciation of the language material as a whole).

3. Speech orientation (perform lexical, grammatical and pronunciation exercises in order to acquire speech activity).

4. Teaching English based on speech samples.

Pedagogical principles of English language teaching in primary grades are described in detail in scientific sources in Uzbek and Russian as a didactic principle. But the pedagogical principle is studied separately in foreign literature. We used scientific sources in three languages to summarize pedagogical principles.

1. Bringing the growing generation to maturity in all aspects. The information acquired through the medium of English and the intellectual and verbal skills and competences acquired during the study of the English language educate students.

2. Encouraging students to use the language being studied.

3. Taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

4. Educate students in the spirit of tolerance towards others and respect for different values.

5. Creating an optimal situation for independent learning of knowledge in lessons.

6. Formation of students' skills and abilities to independently and mutually determine mastery indicators.

7. To create an opportunity for students to demonstrate their knowledge in the studied language.

8. Organization of lessons based on an integrative approach aimed at acquisition of competencies. Every state, every nation is strong not only with its land and natural resources, military power and production potential, but also, first of all, with its high culture and spirituality. Therefore, in order to raise a healthy and well-rounded generation in our republic, great works are being carried out in terms of the scale and scope of the fundamental renewal and reform of the education system.

The multicultural and multilingual "landscape" of Uzbekistan is an effective basis for the development of a person's language competence. English language education or, in the words of N. Galskova, "Linguistic and cultural education" further expands the opportunities and boundaries of the young generation to receive, deliver and interact with new and useful information.

On December 10, 2012, in the decision PQ-1875 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages", improving the system of training the young generation in foreign languages and specialists who can speak these languages fluently, the main goal is to create opportunities for them to widely use the achievements of world civilization and information resources, to develop international cooperation and communication.

The purpose of education can be defined as a socio-pedagogical and linguodidactic concept applied to English language teaching as follows: education in the form of a social order of society and the state to learn English, which is one of the subjects of general education. It is a means of defining the content, organizing the teaching process and determining the achievement of certain results in advance. Why is English taught at school? is a term-concept used as an answer to the question. In comprehensive schools, students are taught English for (1) practical purposes, (2) general educational purposes, (3) educational purposes, and (4) developmental purposes. In order to achieve the practical goal of teaching English, the final practical goal of teaching English in the general education school course is listening and reading, that is, getting information by listening and reading in a foreign language. The intermediate practical goal is interpreted differently: in class I, listening comprehension and speaking are practical goals; In II-IV classes, listening comprehension and speaking is a practical goal, a means of repeating and strengthening language material learned in reading and writing oral speech; In grades V-VI, listening comprehension,

speaking and reading are intermediate practical goals, writing is a practical tool; In grades VII-IX, listening comprehension and reading are practical goals, speaking and writing are tools.

It is known that any goal arises out of necessity. In methodological literature, objective and subjective needs are distinguished based on educational conditions in the analysis of needs. Objective needs: a) age-related psychological characteristics of English language learners, mother tongue, interests, English language learning abilities; b) the levels of knowledge, skills and abilities that must be acquired from speech activities in English; d) based on the state and society's demand, i.e. the social order, it is determined on the basis of information about the programmatic requirements for students' English language knowledge, skills and abilities.

Subjective needs of students: a) attitudes towards the English language and culture; b) English language learning methods and strategies; d) it is analyzed on the basis of information about the types of speech activities (speaking, listening comprehension, reading and writing) they are interested in learning. Educational goals are determined based on analytical data about objective and subjective needs.

When determining educational goals, it is necessary to give priority to the communicative needs of students. A goal is a general direction in education, a plan for solving a specific task(s). A goal is a consciously planned outcome of teaching and learning English and its host culture. Educational goals are a social order - a task, focused on the formation and upbringing of a well-rounded person, which defines the English language teaching system by determining the content of education and the result to be achieved in accordance with it.

The goals of teaching English as the main component of this system are determined based on the conditions of general education and the demands of society and the individual. The goal, in turn, determines the content, principles of English language teaching, as well as the methods and technologies arising from the characteristics of the teacher and students.

In order to achieve the practical goal of teaching English, special topics and language material are selected for the types of speech activity, the main part of the study time is devoted to their study, that is, most of the exercises are performed in this type(s) of speech activity. The practical goal is achieved by acquiring linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies. Competence (ability, quality), as it is known, consists of a set of knowledge, skills, qualifications and personal characteristics. Competence includes small concepts.

Linguistic competence takes into account the use of linguistic phenomena in speech. Sociolinguistic competence involves the ability to express an opinion in accordance with the communication situation, purpose and tasks of the interlocutors. Pragmatic concept refers to the ability to control oneself in a communicative situation (for example, to ask repeatedly, to be able to get out of it when speech and linguistic complexity arises). Discursive competence within pragmatic competence serves to ensure consistency in oral and written speech. The integral integrity (synthesis) of all the competencies formed in the realization of the practical goal is ensured. In the realization of the practical goal, the student is educated, brought up and his personality develops. In the realization of the general educational goal of English language teaching, it is envisaged to acquire useful life information and new simple information about the language through the studied language tool. Raising the general level of the student, gaining new information about the studied language and culture, improving communication culture, using mental work methods, and developing thinking qualities are achieved. In the implementation of this goal, mainly linguistic, strategic (compensatory), educational-cognitive, discursive qualities

are improved. Among other subjects, English also contributes to general education as a compulsory subject. The object of general education is threefold: the phenomenon of language, its concept or simple rule, and most importantly, the content of discourse in English.

The educational purpose of teaching English. The essence of this goal is to provide students with ideological education, inculcate mental work skills, and increase their cognitive activity. The educational goal is mainly realized in two ways: (1) direct greetings and farewells in a foreign language, knowing the names of objects and events, reciting poems and songs, playing games, etc., especially for students in the first lessons is considered a very interesting task; (2) to be able to relate to each other within the framework of etiquette during communication, to be able to interpret their behavior, the information obtained from audio text and graphic texts is of incomparable educational value. The educational value of extracurricular activities is also unlimited.

Developmental purpose of teaching English. It is consistent with the meaning of developmental education in didactics and represents the development of mental, emotional and motivational aspects of the student's personality. The student can be intellectually and spiritually nourished, tests his feelings in speech communication, learns the opinions of interlocutors (students, teachers, announcers, etc.) and expresses his own opinion. Overcoming normal linguistic and speech difficulties in the educational process, including learning English, ensures the development of the student's thinking and feelings.

The developmental goal is achieved only through speech acts. Its serious difference from the general educational goal is that education is conceptually connected with the acquisition of educational information, the content of information serves to form various competencies. Education, including learning English, occupies a special place in the development of a person. As a psychological, communicative, functional and cultural phenomenon, language is very important for the process of knowledge, because it is a factor that leads from ignorance to knowledge. In English, the student acquires two types of knowledge, the first and the main one is the necessary algorithmic rules for participation in the speech process and useful information during the student's life, which acquires social significance. Intercultural communication serves to inculcate the characteristics and customs of the mentality of another nation. In this way, he learns not to advertise the lifestyle of others, but to look at the world in a new way through the eyes of an English speaker and, as a result, to deeply feel his own culture. Universal and national values will be combined.

The quality and effectiveness of any education depends on the level of accuracy in defining the goal. Practical (primary), general educational, educational and developmental goals are recognized in teaching English. The main goal of English language teaching at all levels of education in our country is to form communicative competence in English for students to work in everyday, scientific and professional spheres in a multicultural world.

Based on the experience gained in developed democratic countries and the rapidly changing requirements of the present, English is taught in our country on the basis of an integrative approach aimed at communicative activity, individual-oriented acquisition of competence. That is, teaching English in primary grades:

- in the words of our First President, to "fully open up opportunities for students to easily enter the wonderful world of foreign languages" and provide education and upbringing at the level of international standards;

- formation of a well-rounded personality, development of the student's speech and language skills, as well as psychological aspects such as attention, perception, memory;

- forming a positive attitude to learning English in students, instilling in them self-confidence, enjoyment and pride in learning English;

- to create conditions for communicative and psychological adaptation of students to the world of a new language from an early age, to eliminate psychological barriers that prevent the use of English as a means of communication;

- to interest students in English language learning activities and to form in them the inclination to acquire communicative competence in English;

- formation of basic skills of oral (listening and speaking) and written (reading and writing) communication in English within the scope of students' speech capabilities and needs;

- to familiarize students with the colorfulness of language and culture, to form in them the character of sincere and tolerant attitude towards different cultures;

- to introduce students to the world of their peers in the country(s) where the language is being studied, examples of folklore and literature, and to teach them to understand and respect universal values from childhood;

- to make students enjoy the cultural heritage created by the master of the studied language;

- the country where the students are learning the language;

- formation of students' initial ideas about the behavior, character, moral standards, customs, customs and traditions of the people of the country whose language is being studied;

- to improve the previously acquired social, cultural, linguistic and emotional experience of the student in the process of acquiring the skills and abilities of listening and reading, expressing thoughts orally and in writing;

- it is aimed at such goals as creating a solid foundation for forming the student's pronunciation without accent and the skills to express his thoughts in a foreign language at a level close to natural speech⁹. English language teaching in elementary grades is a cooperative activity of the teacher and the student, striving from the goal to the result. In primary education, the following tasks are performed to achieve the goal:

- two types of knowledge for the student, i.e., algorithmic rules related to the language (phonetics, graphics and orthography, lexicon, grammar) necessary for participation in the speech process, and information that will be useful throughout the student's life is given;

- the student is taught to look at the world scene in a new way through the eyes of an English speaker and, as a result, to feel the harmony of universal and national values;

- four types of speech activities through exercises such as reading and writing, reading and listening, reading and speaking, listening and reading, listening and writing, listening and speaking: listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing skills are interlinked.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training" are all conditions for the priority of human interests, their increasing needs and interests, and the full realization of their capabilities in accordance with the requirements of the times was adopted in order to create conditions, strengthen democratic values in the minds of the growing generation, to form a mature and independent thinking person who has his own opinion, his views and a firm civic (citizen) position.

The state policy in the field of personnel training envisages the formation of a well-rounded person - a citizen through the continuous education system, which is inextricably linked with the

intellectual, spiritual and moral education of a person. Today, educational programs and textbooks for grades 1-4, taking into account the psychophysiological characteristics of children of this age, are being critically revised based on the concept of individual-oriented education and the competence approach.

With the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" and the Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 124 dated May 8, 2013, each State educational standards of the continuous education system, which provide clear criteria for the level of knowledge of foreign languages at the educational stage, were approved, and starting from the 2013/2014 academic year, the study of foreign languages, mainly English, in the republic gradually began from the first grades of general education schools. was introduced. This paragraph defines the term approach and analyzes approaches to teaching English. Also, a general description of the communicative approach in teaching English to elementary school students, linguistic and psychological bases and principles of the theory of communicative competence will be covered. The role and importance of the communicative approach in primary English language education is determined. In this paragraph, we used the abbreviations KYO (communicative approach), KK (communicative competence).

An approach is a set of concepts related to the characteristics of language teaching and learning. The approach is axiomatic. It represents the content of the taught subject.

The term "approach" is defined in dictionaries in the sense that it is based on a certain theory in order to solve an issue or find a solution to a problem. In English language teaching methodology, this term was first used by Edward Mason Anthony, a professor at the University of Michigan in the USA, in order to express the laws related to the nature of the language and its learning/teaching methods, and the following definitions were given to it:

An approach is a set of correlative assumptions dealing with the nature of language teaching and learning. An approach is axiomatic. It describes the nature of the subject matter to be taught....

Approach: Theoretically well-informed positions and beliefs about the nature of language, the nature of language learning, and the applicability of both to pedagogical settings.

The approach is a theoretically well-explained position and point of view about the content of language teaching and the nature of language learning, as well as the possibilities of introducing them into the pedagogical process.

According to Anthony, an approach is a set of principles or concepts about language, its learning and teaching that are refined by taking into account the characteristics of its learning and teaching, and it is adapted to a method or theoretically based on it. That is, the term approach refers to the theory of language and language learning that serves as the source of English language teaching practices and principles.

The approach is a fundamental component at the core of the language teaching system, embodied as a general methodological basis of teaching and the existing educational content of the purpose, tasks of the (language) subject and the possibility of their implementation in the educational process. characterized by points of view.

According to methodologists, the approach summarizes views on the content of educational science (Vyatyuntnev, 1984), is used as a general methodological basis for research

in the field of concrete knowledge (Bim, 1984), determines the direction of the researcher's activity in the study of one or another phenomenon (Skalkin, 1981).

There is no single classification of approach in the methodology. For example, M.V. Lyakhovitsky (1981) classifies approaches from a psycholinguistic point of view as follows:

Behaviouristic - language is learned through the method of forming speech automatisms in response to external stimuli;

Inductive-conscious - the language is learned through the acquisition of language laws and methods of their use in speech as a result of analytical observation of speech patterns;

Conscious (cognitive) - the language is learned in the consistency of formation of speech skills and abilities based on acquired knowledge;

Integrative - organizationally coordinates conscious and unconscious components in the process of language teaching, that is, English is learned through the parallel acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities.

Taking into account the linguistic factors of language learning, M.N. Vyatyutnev divides the approaches to classification of modern methods into 6 types: grammatical, correct, behavioral, educational, collective, communicative, individualized types. J.S.Richards, T.S.Rodgerds, D.Brown, D.L.Freeman in researching methods to theories about language (structural, functional and interactive) and language learning, that is: a) psychological and cognitive processes that play an important role in language learning ; b) refer to situations that activate the language learning process and factors that optimize it.

General classification of communicative approach (KYO).

KYO for teaching English is formed on the basis of the communicative method that has been developing since 1960. American and British experts recognize that communicative English teaching is not a method, but an approach, and that communicative competence should be the goal of language teaching, to ensure the interdependence between language and communication, all began to promote the need for integrative development of knowledge, skills and abilities from speech activities.

By the 1960s, audiolingual and situational approaches to English language teaching had passed their time, the linguistic theories developed on their basis did not meet the requirements of the time, and the communicative and functional characteristics of individual sentences were inadequately interpreted in these theories promoting structure. articles and theses of authors such as N. Chomsky, K. Kendlin, H. Windowson, T. Pika, R. Oxford about the need to prioritize the development of communicative skills in English language teaching rather than memorizing the structure (speech patterns) was published. In this context, the concept of "Learning to use English and using English to learn it" was developed.

This concept, first of all, requires extensive use of model, standard phrases, basic lexical units and linguistic functions in training. It is also required to use English language in organizing the lesson, recording the attendance in the journal, evaluating the students, encouraging them, giving guidance, instructions and recommendations regarding the correct completion of the task and communicating with each other. Such integration occurs due to the use of memorized ready-made and semi-ready standard template sentences in different speech situations.

Before this concept was developed, different, often conflicting, opinions of experts regarding the essence of the issue of what to teach in the educational process were being explained.

There are two problems in this regard: first, when answering the question of what is taught, most scientists give the correct but general answer that the content of education is taught.

In 1971-1972, studies were carried out in order to improve educational courses for learning English. The members of the group headed by D.A. Wilkins analyzed the needs of Europeans to learn English and developed a communicative curriculum. Later, Wilkins published a special collection summarizing the research materials, and this book had a significant impact on the popularization of the theory of developing linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competences of learners by introducing a communicative approach to English language teaching.

According to V.A. Sukhomlinsky, a teacher who can forget that he is a teacher is the best teacher. The meaning behind these words is expressed in English lessons. For this, it is necessary to give up the advice tone, show genuine interest in the students and their words, forget that you are one step above, and stand side by side with the student. Only then will the student's interest increase, he will have a desire to talk, and as a result, communication and interaction will take place during classes.

In KY, both the object of learning and the means of learning are communication, that is, communicative competence is acquired through communication. According to KYO, language is learned in the process of using it. In English language teaching, based on KYO, the goal and task of the subject of education should be to form knowledge of foreign languages in everyday, scientific and professional spheres of the learners in a multicultural and multicultural world.

In the literature, there are opinions about the possibility of applying KY to adult language learners and in the context of the natural environment of the English language being studied. In our opinion, KYO can be adapted to the conditions of primary classes where education is conducted in the Uzbek language. Because elementary school students are in the stage of obvious operations of their youth, i.e. in the stage of discovering and learning in the process of communication and interaction. Taking into account the sociability and eagerness to demonstrate what they know, characteristic of students in the clear operations stage of their age, it is appropriate to apply KY in the process of teaching English in primary education.

To prove our point, let's look at the linguistic foundations of KYo. Linguistic foundations of the communicative approach to teaching English in primary education.

Linguistic foundations of KYo: The communicative approach to English language teaching was developed on the basis of the concept of communicative competence introduced into the linguistic discourse by A.N. Chomsky and D. Haiman and the theory that language is a means of communication. The term KK consists of two words, communication - exchange of ideas or information; competence means a set of necessary knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure good awareness of a field or issue and successful operation in this field. The term competence refers to qualities, qualities and characteristics that enable a person to work in a certain field.

The speaker's (listener's) competence should make him/her able to compose (understand) an unlimited number of sentences based on models, as well as be able to make rational judgments, taking into account the similarities and differences between languages. We also paid attention to the root of the word "compete" which means to compete, to compete, to compete. If this core concept is taken into account, the meaning of the word competence deepens and it expresses the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure the competitiveness of a specialist for successful operation in a certain field based on different definitions, KK is to be able to successfully compete with the interlocutor in effective communication to achieve a certain goal,

to be able to use language adequately to share information, ideas, points of view, thoughts, imagination and inner experiences, it is possible to form a definition that the provider is a set of necessary knowledge, skills and abilities.

The definition of KK is based on research carried out within the framework of the European Union "Language Learning for European Citizenship" program (Strasbourg, 1996) and CEFR.

- It was developed in detail during the preparation of the document, which is one of the international norms on "Pan-European competences of foreign language acquisition: learning, teaching, assessment". CEFR defines competence and communicative language competence as follows:

Competences are the sum of knowledge, skills and characteristics that allow a person to perform actions.

Communicative language competences are those which empower a person to act using specifically linguistic means.

KK is the ability to use acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of communication. KK consists of a set of linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies, and several other competencies are included in these competencies. Today, when English is recognized as the main goal of teaching English, acquisition of KK has led to the recognition of communication as the main teaching tool and competence as the educational goal.

The uniqueness of the linguistic theory of communicative competence is manifested in the following aspects:

1. Language is a system of expressing meaning.
2. The main function of language is interaction and communication.
3. Language structure reflects its functional and communicative use.
4. The main language units are not their grammatical and structural function, but the category of functional and communicative meaning defined in the discourse.

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